

ISic2830

I.Sicily inscription 2830

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

sandstone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Cephaloedium

Place of origin (modern)

Cefalù

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Cefalù, Museo Mandralisca

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR108738

1. []κλε [.]

2. χαῖρε

Edition: PHI331218

1. ²vestigia litterarum²

2. [— —]οκλεῖ ²⁷[— —]OKΛ vacat (L. Moretti, photo)²⁷

3. χαῖρε.

4.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284833

EDR 108738

EDCS 64900514

PHI 331218

Bibliography

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